

Supplementary information for

Voronota-LT: efficient, flexible and solvent-aware tessellation-based analysis of atomic interactions

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S1 Supplementary algorithmic aspects

S1.1 Constrained Voronoi cell characterization algorithm

To compute the total solvent-accessible area corresponding to the constrained Voronoi cell, we use the fact that the area of a region on a sphere surface can be directly calculated from the solid angle subtended by the region from the sphere center. Instead of computing the solid angle of the solvent-accessible surface directly, we compute the solid angles for all the atom-atom contact surfaces, sum them up, and subtract the sum from the total solid angle of a sphere that equals 4π steradians. As every our contact is a convex polygon with sides that are either line segments or circular arcs, we can compute every contact-subtended solid angle analytically. There is a pitfall in the radical Voronoi tessellation when the sphere’s center lies outside the sphere’s Voronoi cell, which can make the solid angles subtended by the cell faces from the sphere’s center overlap. We handle such overlaps by inverting solid angle values (subtracting them from 4π) where needed.

Knowing the total solid angle of the solvent-accessible regions also allows us to compute the volume of the corresponding spherical sector inside the contact sphere. To get the total volume of the constrained Voronoi cell, we add the total sum of volumes of the pyramids formed by using the sphere’s center as the apex and the contact surfaces as bases. In cases when the sphere’s center lies outside the Voronoi cell, the pyramids can overlap. Therefore, we invert pyramid volumes (multiply them by -1) where needed. The process of calculating both the volume and the solvent-accessible area of a constrained Voronoi cell is detailed in pseudocode in Algorithm S1.

S1.2 Contacts updating algorithm

Consider a scenario where we have a set of atomic balls with an associated set of constructed contacts, and we need to modify (move or resize) a subset of these balls and subsequently update the contacts. Based on our definition of contacts, the modification of the balls can affect the following categories of contacts: the contacts between the modified balls; the contacts between the modified balls and their close-enough neighbors (close-enough before or after the modification); the contacts between the close-enough neighbors of the modified balls. Any other contacts cannot be affected because the modified balls cannot interfere with them. Let us denote the set of indices of the modified balls as I_m . The modified balls can have different sets of close-enough neighbors before and after the modification: let I_n^1 represent the indices of close-enough neighbors before the modification and I_n^2 the indices of close-enough neighbors after the modification. The overall set of indices of the balls relevant to updating the contacts is $I = I_m \cup I_n^1 \cup I_n^2$. This allows us to define the contact update procedure in Voronota-LT as a simple two-step process: before modifying the balls, delete all the contacts between any pair of balls whose indices are both in I ; after the modification of balls, reconstruct all possible contacts between any pair of balls whose indices are both in I . The process of updating balls and contacts is detailed in pseudocode in Algorithm S2.

S2 Supplementary benchmarking

S2.1 Correlation between differently calculated contact areas

We computed the Pearson correlation coefficients between sets of areas calculated using different methods for every input structure (Table S1). We summarized every distribution of coefficients by calculating the minimal (ρ_{\min}) and the average (ρ_{avg}) values. When all the input ball radii were set to 1.8 Å, the vanilla Voronota and Voronota-LT contact areas correlated ideally ($\rho_{\min} = 1$, $\rho_{\text{avg}} = 1$), as expected. When the radii were not changed to be the same, the vanilla Voronota and Voronota-LT-AW contact areas correlated almost ideally ($\rho_{\min} = 0.999$, $\rho_{\text{avg}} = 1$) — we attribute the slight differences to the usage of triangulated approximations of surfaces for computing areas.

Because the differences between van der Waals radii of different atoms in biological macromolecular structures are not extreme, contact areas based on the radical and additively weighted Voronoi tessellations were expected to correlate highly. Indeed, vanilla Voronota and Voronota-LT-Radical contact areas correlated with $\rho_{\min} = 0.9609$ and $\rho_{\text{avg}} = 0.976$, the histogram of coefficients is presented in Fig. S2. Interestingly, the contact areas summarized on the residue-residue level correlated even higher ($\rho_{\min} = 0.9947$, $\rho_{\text{avg}} = 0.999$). The summarized chain-chain areas correlated even better (Fig. S3), the Pearson correlation coefficient calculated for all 67,700 interfaces in the benchmark dataset was greater than 0.9999. Solvent-accessible surface areas computed by vanilla Voronota and Voronota-LT also correlated almost ideally ($\rho_{\min} = 0.9997$, $\rho_{\text{avg}} = 1$).

S2.2 Performance of contacts updating

We used the previously introduced set of 14,861 PDB structures to benchmark the average time it takes Voronota-LT to update the set of contacts and the set of atomic cell descriptors after moving atoms of a single residue (in the analyzed set, on average, one residue has 7.9 atoms). For every input structure, we repeated 500 times the following iteration that involved two updates: moved a randomly selected residue in a randomly sampled direction by a distance randomly sampled from the [1.0; 5.0] Å interval; updated the contacts and the cells; moved the perturbed residue back; updated the contacts and the cells. We recorded the calculation times and confirmed that there were no accumulated errors — the contacts and the cells before and after all the perturbing/restoring modifications were identical. The recorded times are presented in Fig. S6. Using a single thread it usually takes 3-5 seconds to perform 1000 residue updates. However, the updating procedure benefits from parallelization — using 10 OpenMP threads, 1000 residue updates usually take less than one second.

Supplementary algorithms

Algorithm S1: Calculate solvent-accessible surface area and volume of a constrained Voronoi cell

Data:

s = probe-expanded sphere that corresponds to the central ball for the Voronoi cell
 C = list of all the contacts of the Voronoi cell

Result:

A = solvent-accessible surface area of the constrained Voronoi cell
 V = volume of the constrained Voronoi cell

```
1  $o$  = center of  $s$ 
2  $r$  = radius of  $s$ 
3  $\Phi = 0$ 
4  $\Omega = 0$ 
5  $q_1 = false$ 
6  $m$  = calculate mass center of the polygons of the contacts in  $C$ 
7 for  $\forall c \in C$  do // checking if the sphere center lies outside the Voronoi cell
8    $p$  = plane corresponding to the contact  $c$ 
9    $q_1$  = check if  $o$  and  $m$  lie in the different halfspaces defined by  $p$ 
10  if  $q_1$  is true then
11    break
12 for  $\forall c \in C$  do
13    $P$  = polygon describing the atom-atom surface of the contact  $c$  (as constructed with
14     Algorithm 2)
15    $\phi$  = calculate the solid angle subtended by  $P$  from  $o$ 
16    $Y$  = the pyramid formed by using  $o$  as the apex and  $P$  as the base
17    $\omega$  = calculate the volume of the pyramid  $Y$ 
18   if  $q_1$  is true then // if the sphere center lies outside the Voronoi cell
19     for  $\forall k \in C, k \neq c$  do
20        $q_2$  = check if  $Y$  intersects the surface of the contact  $k$ 
21       if  $q_2$  is true then
22          $\phi = 4\pi - \phi$ 
23          $\omega = -\omega$ 
24         break
25    $\Phi = \Phi + \phi$ 
26    $\Omega = \Omega + \omega$ 
27  $\Psi = 4\pi - \Phi$ 
28 while  $\Psi < 0$  do
29    $\Psi = \Psi + 4\pi$ 
30  $A = r^2\Psi$ 
31  $V = \Omega + (r^3\Psi/3)$ 
return ( $A, V$ )
```

Algorithm S2: Update balls and contacts

Data:

B = list of balls before updating
 S = list of probe-expanded spheres corresponding to B
 G = spatial indexing grid of spheres in S_1 (computed in Algorithm 1)
 M = map of lists of presorted close-enough neighbors for spheres in S_1 (computed in Algorithm 1)
 C = list of constructed contacts before updating
 I_m = list of indices of balls to modify
 T_m = list of coordinate and radius transformations to be applied to B_1 and S_1 for every index in I

Result:

B = list of balls after updating
 S = list of probe-expanded spheres corresponding to B after updating
 G = spatial indexing grid of spheres in S after updating
 M = map of lists of presorted close-enough neighbors for spheres in S after updating
 C = list of constructed contacts after updating

```
1  $I_n^1$  = empty list
2 for  $\forall i_m \in I_m$  do // collect indices of neighbors before updating balls
3    $I_n^1 = I_n^1 \cup M[i_m]$ 
4 for  $\forall i_m \in I_m$  do // update spatial indexing grid
5    $G = G$  with  $S[i_m]$  removed
6 for  $\forall (i_m, t_m) \in (I_m, T_m)$  do // update balls and the corresponding spheres
7    $B[i_m] =$  apply  $t_m$  to  $B[i_m]$ 
8    $S[i_m] =$  apply  $t_m$  to  $S[i_m]$ 
9 for  $\forall i_m \in I_m$  do // update spatial indexing grid
10   $G = G$  with  $S[i_m]$  inserted
11 for  $\forall i \in (I_m \cup I_n^1)$  do // update map of lists of close-enough neighbors
12   $M[i] =$  list of indices of all spheres in  $S$  that intersect  $S[i]$ , collected using  $G$  (like in
   Algorithm 1)
13  $I_n^2$  = empty list
14 for  $\forall i_m \in I_m$  do // collect indices of neighbors after updating balls
15   $I_n^2 = I_n^2 \cup M[i_m]$ 
16  $I = I_m \cup I_n^1 \cup I_n^2$  // collect all indices of balls for updating contacts
17 for  $\forall c \in C$  do // remove possibly affected contacts
18    $(i_1, i_2) =$  indices of balls in the contact described by  $c$ 
19   if  $i_1 \in I$  and  $i_2 \in I$  then
20      $C = C$  with  $c$  removed
21 for  $\forall i_1 \in I$  do // construct and add missing contacts
22   for  $\forall i_2 \in M[i_1], i_1 < i_2$  do
23      $c =$  construct contact between  $B[i_1]$  and  $B[i_2]$  (using Algorithm 2)
24     if  $c$  constructed successfully then
25        $C = C$  with  $c$  added
26 return  $(B, S, G, M, C)$ 
```

Supplementary figures

```

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Fig. S1. RCSB GraphQL query used to download a list of PDB entities to get PDB entry identifiers for the benchmarking of Voronota-LT.

Fig. S2. Correlation between contact areas computed by vanilla Voronota and Voronota-LT on atom-atom and residue-residue levels.

Fig. S3. Correlation between inter-chain interface contact areas computed by vanilla Voronota and Voronota-LT.

Fig. S4. Distributions of maximum and mean differences of per-atom volumes calculated by Voronota-LT and SBL-Vorlume for the analyzed protein structures.

Fig. S5. Examples of the Voronoi-Laguerre tessellation-derived contacts computed for several crystals from the Crystallography Open Database (COD). The contacts (colored in yellow) were computed for the unit cell atomic balls (colored in blue) considering the periodic boundary conditions defined by the crystal lattice vectors (indicated using the gray lines). The relevant COD entry identifiers are displayed above every example.

**Update time per 1000 residue updates
(log scale for atoms, linear scale for seconds)**

Fig. S6. Performance of the Voronota-LT update procedure.

Fig. S7. Example application of Voronota-LT for studying inter-chain interface contact variability in an ensemble of dimeric protein structures. We analysed an NMR ensemble of 20 conformational states taken from the Protein Data Bank entry 1CIR deposited by the authors of the study on chymotrypsin inhibitor 2 folding (Neira et al., 1996). It is a dimeric protein molecule, and we focused on the contacts in the inter-chain interface. We computed the contact areas and, for every unique contact, we calculated the mean and the variance values of the corresponding observed area distribution. We considered both atom-atom contact areas and the residue-residue level areas derived by summing atom-atom areas according to residue identifiers. We visualized the results by displaying inter-chain contact surfaces and coloring them by the corresponding variance-to-mean ratios (relative variances) that indicate how much every contact area is dispersed relative to its mean. We observed what contact areas varied the least and the most. In particular, the contact areas further from the solvent, in the interface core, were more stable. The most variable interface region involved interactions with a C-terminal tail of chain A. 3D visualizations were generated using Voronota-GL.

Supplementary tables

Table S1. Summary of Pearson correlation coefficients between differently produced sets of areas for every input structure. We summarized every distribution of coefficients by calculating the minimal and the average values. For a more convenient display, the values were rounded up to four significant digits. Note that vanilla Voronota always uses triangulated approximations of surfaces for computing areas, while Voronota-LT uses triangulated approximations only in the additively-weighted (AW) tessellation mode.

Regime	Method 1	Method 2	Pearson coeff.	
			minimal	average
atom-atom area	Voronota-Vanilla-AW	Voronota-LT-Radical	0.9609	0.9843
atom-atom area	Voronota-Vanilla-AW	Voronota-LT-AW	0.9990	1
atom-atom area using uniform radii	Voronota-Vanilla-AW	Voronota-LT-Radical	1	1
residue-residue area	Voronota-Vanilla-AW	Voronota-LT-Radical	0.9947	0.9990
SAS area	Voronota-Vanilla-AW	Voronota-LT-Radical	0.9997	1

Table S2. Voronota-LT processing times for all the PDB models (not biological assemblies) available from <https://files.wwpdb.org/pub/pdb/data/structures/all/pdb/> on 2025-01-20, using 16 cores on a desktop workstation (Intel® Xeon® Silver 4210R CPU @ 2.40GHz, Ubuntu Linux 23.04).

Dataset	Number of models	Total number of heavy atoms	Voronota-LT running mode	Processing time using 16 CPU cores
All PDB models	222,807	1,429,357,248	default (calculates all atom-atom contact areas, all per-atom SASA, all per-atom volumes)	91 minute
All multi-chain PDB models	146,590	1,270,213,285	inter-chain (calculates all inter-chain atom-atom contract areas)	20 minutes